

Design of a 6-bit CMOS Digital Radio Frequency Memory

Gordon M. Kranz
Avionics Systems Engineer
ASD/ENA

Mark Mehalic
Director, Center for VLSI Research
AFIT/ENG

Abstract

This paper describes the implementation of a Digital Radio Frequency Memory (DRFM) on a single integrated circuit. A VHSIC Hardware Description Language (VHDL) model of the DRFM was completed and used to design the VLSI components of the DRFM architecture. The model was simulated and shown to perform the specified time and frequency shift functions. A DRFM, with a 1K memory, a control unit, and a Digital Single-Sideband Modulator (DSSM), has been placed onto a silicon single chip layout design.

Introduction

A DRFM is a digital device typically used in airborne Electronic Warfare applications to jam enemy radars. Wright Labs is conducting DRFM related research to determine potential capabilities and in implementing a DRFM on a single integrated circuit. The current focus is on having the DRFM receive an RF signal, time and frequency shift the signal and retransmit the modified, false, radar return. The enemy radar would lock on to the false signal and gather incorrect information about the friendly aircraft. Several AFIT research efforts have been conducted to define the ba-

sic DRFM architecture. The result of one effort was the design of a DSSM to implement a frequency shift capability [1]. Another effort developed the design for a dual-port memory architecture for implementing a time delay feature [2]. The result of these efforts is a prototype DRFM which occupies several standard racks of equipment and uses hundreds of off-the-shelf ICs.

This paper discusses the simulation and design of a 6-bit CMOS Digital Radio Frequency Memory (DRFM) [3]. The purpose of this research was to reduce the size of previously designed components. The ultimate goal of the AFIT VLSI research group is to develop a DRFM on a single VLSI integrated circuit with the following functions: 1) analog-to-digital and digital-to-analog conversion; 2) digital filtering to implement a programmable frequency shift capability [1]; and 3) digital data storage to implement a time delay capability [2]. Future research will focus on providing additional capability such as a processor interface to the data in the memory allowing for Digital Signal Processing (DSP) of the data, increasing the potential radar jamming capabilities of the DRFM. The purpose of this particular study was to provide a foundation for achieving the objectives outlined above. Specifically, a VHDL description of

a DRFM was developed; a VLSI dual-port CMOS memory was designed, fabricated and tested; and a DRFM on a single VLSI circuit was designed which implements the time delay and frequency shift DRFM capabilities.

System Architecture

This DRFM architecture is pipelined and consists of two multiplexed channels operating at 50 MHz to achieve an effective operating rate of 100 MHz. The design presented here is for one of these 50 MHz channels. The pipelined architecture allows a full clock cycle processing time for each pipeline stage. The memory and control unit components of the DRFM form the first pipeline stage and the second pipeline stage consists of the digital single-sideband modulator components of the DRFM. Figure 1 shows the pipelined nature of the DRFM. The pipeline stages are separated by a latch placed between the output of the memory and the input to the digital single-sideband modulator.

Interfaces

A system level overview of the DRFM operation is provided by describing the external interfaces shown in Figure 1.

Data Input Lines - These input lines are for the down converted, analog-to-digital converted, radio frequency input signal. This design has six input bits.

Data Output Lines - Six output bits, represent the delayed, frequency shifted data, which will be converted back to analog and re-transmitted. Valid data will be output every clock cycle after the pipeline has been filled and the requested delay has been met.

Reset - This signal is the system initialization signal, used to set the programmable time delay in the DRFM. When this signal is asserted the control unit is loaded with initial read and write addresses. The initial write address is $3FF_{16}$ and the initial read address is the complement of the delay request lines. This process offsets the read and write addresses by the amount

requested by effectively performing a twos complement subtraction between the read and write addresses.

Delay Request Lines - This input port is ten bits wide, its purpose is to allow the user to input the number of clock cycles of desired delay to inject into the input signal.

PQ1 and PQ2 Clock Signals - Dual phase non-overlapping clocks are used in this design to control the DRFM timing. The period of PQ1 controls the speed of the DRFM operation, each pipeline stage is provided new data every PQ1 clock pulse. PQ2 is used internally to gate data to intermediate points setting up for the PQ1 pulse.

Precharge - This input signal is used to control the precharging of the bit lines within the memory array during a read cycle. This signal and the chip select signal should be mutually exclusive signals to prevent the corruption of the data contained in the memory. The assertion of these signals is externally controlled.

Chip Select - This input signal is used to gate the row address of the memory. Both the read and write address will be gated simultaneously. The dual port memory design allows a simultaneous read and write from the same memory array.¹

Components

The components shown in Figure 1 are described below:

Memory

The memory component is a 1K by 6-bit dual-port static RAM. The memory architecture defines one port as read only and one port as write only. The outputs, word lines, of two independent decoders access data contained in a single memory array. The delay function of the DRFM is implemented by offsetting the read and write addresses. The read address

¹ The two phase clocks could meet the requirements of the chip select and precharge signals.

follows the write address by the number specified by the delay request lines. The size of the memory constrains the amount of delay: for this design the largest delay is 1023 clock cycles and the smallest delay is one clock cycle.

Control Unit

The control unit supplies the read and write addresses to the memory. The control unit determines the address offset required to implement the time delay requested by the user. The control unit initializes the write address bits to all ones and the read address bits to the complement of the input delay bits. This process effectively performs a twos complement subtraction, and offsets the read address from the write address by an integer number of clock cycles. The value of the delay request lines, determines the number of clock cycles to delay the output data.

Digital Single-Sideband Modulator

The digital single side-band modulator implements the frequency shifting property of the DRFM. A single-sideband modulator modulates a signal to a specific frequency then filters out either the lower or upper sideband prior to transmission. The modulator design is taken from the work done by Capt Foltz [1]. The VLSI components used to implement this design are a Hilbert transform, a multiplier, an in-phase delay element, and an adder. The basic operation is that the data read out of the memory (see Figure 1) is simultaneously passed to the Hilbert transform and the in-phase delay. The in-phase delay will synchronize the in-phase data with the Hilbert transform output. The output of the in-phase delay is multiplied by a cosine signal at the frequency of the desired frequency shift. The output of the Hilbert transform is the input data phase shifted by 90 degrees. This output is multiplied by a sine signal of the same frequency as the cosine signal. The multiplier outputs are either added or subtracted. If added the lower sideband is filtered out, if subtracted the upper sideband is filtered out.

DRFM VHDL Simulation

The VLSI DRFM was described using the VH-SIC Description Language (VHDL) [4]. The VHDL description allowed for the detailed design of the control unit and provides a simulation tool to use in system modeling and design verification. The system was described by writing code to simulate each of the DRFM components, then configuring the components into a single system by describing the component interconnections. A VHDL description identifies the interfaces and operation of a system component. The operation of each component can be described in several ways. A component's behavior can be described at the black box level or can be described by identifying and describing its subcomponents. The first way of describing a component is referred to as a behavioral description, and the second way is referred to as a structural description of the component. The components of the DRFM were described using the behavioral description except for the control unit which was described using a structural description. The VHDL model not only provides a system view of the DRFM operation, but also of the operation of the DRFM components.

Figure 2 shows the transfer function of the Hilbert transform component of the DRFM. These results are consistent with theoretical data evaluated by Foltz [1]. The f in the figure is nf_s/N , where f_s is 1 MHz and N is 1024.

Figure 3 shows the frequency response of the DRFM to a 125 kHz sinusoidal input signal. The output signal is shifted by 25 kHz, which is the frequency of the externally provided sine and cosine signals. The upper/lower sideband is not totally filtered out due mainly to the quantization error introduced by the analog-to-digital conversion.

The time delay feature of the DRFM is shown by Figure 4. Part of the delay (10 clock cycles) is due to the inherent delay in the Hilbert transform to make the filter causal, and part of the delay is due to the offset read and write addresses.

Test Chips

The design philosophy used was to design each of the components independently, verify and fabricate each component separately. The fabricated chips were tested to determine their performance. After the components were verified they were integrated into a single chip design. The Hilbert transform, and multiplier components of the digital single-sideband modulator were fabricated and tested as they exist in the DRFM system design. The memory component was fabricated as a functionally equivalent test chip containing 32 8 bit words. This allowed the designs for the decoders, sense amplifiers, memory cells, and address and data input drivers to be verified. The design for the DRFM differs only in the row column selection scheme and amount of memory contained in the component (1K of 6-bit words).

Hilbert Transform

This component was fabricated in a $2\mu\text{m}$ process. Testing showed that it performs the required 90 degree phase shift of an input signal [5]. This component is used as designed and fabricated in the DRFM system design.

Multiplier

This component was also fabricated in a $2\mu\text{m}$ process. Testing showed that it performed the multiply function correctly but, it was not as fast as expected. The design will not be revised prior to the fabrication of version one of the single chip DRFM design, since the purpose of the first chip is to prove the basic functional implementation of a DRFM on a single chip. This chip will be used to build a test bench for additional research and will be revised through this effort. Future revisions will concentrate on speeding the components of the chip.

Memory

The memory design is a dual-port CMOS memory with one port dedicated as a read port and the other port designated as a write port. The test chip consisted of 32 8-bit memory

words. The purpose of designing a scaled down version of the memory was to verify the memory component designs (ie. decoders, memory cells, sense amplifiers, etc.). Testing of the 32-word memory chip was limited due to the lack of availability of an automated VLSI chip tester. The decoder, sense amplifier, and data and address driver functions were all tested. The read and write operation could not be fully verified due to an error in the memory cell layout. The test chip was fabricated in a 40 pin package. Two power pins, two ground pins, 10 address pins, one chip select pin, one precharge signal pin, 8 data input, and 8 data output pins were required for the operation of the chip. This left 8 pins for test pins. The test pins were connected to internal points within the memory architecture to provide visibility into subcomponent operation. The DRFM system memory is a 1K by 6-bit architecture.

Single-chip DRFM

After each of the components was designed and verified they were integrated into a single chip design. The layout was done in a signal flow fashion. The data enters the chip from one side and is passed through the components of the DRFM to the output on the other side of the chip. Figure 5 shows the silicon floor plan of the designed DRFM chip. The current size is 7900 by 7900 μm , given a $2\mu\text{m}$ fabrication process. Fabrication of the single chip DRFM is scheduled to be complete by early May 1991.

Summary

The single chip DRFM described in this article is ready for fabrication. VHDL simulations of the single chip DRFM show that the frequency shifting and time delay functions of the DRFM are implemented. Analog simulations show that the speed of the memory and control unit, stage one of the pipelined architecture, is about 22-25 ns. Testing has shown that the designed components of the digital single sideband modulator, stage two of the pipelined architecture, operates in about 40 ns. The chip will be fabricated as currently

designed to show the functions of the single chip DRFM. Future research efforts will focus on meeting the speed requirements and providing additional capabilities.

References

- [1] Foltz, Thomas M. *A Digital Single-Sideband Modulator for a Digital Radio Frequency Memory*. MS thesis, AFIT/GE/ENG/88D-12. School of Engineering, Air Force Institute of Technology (AU), Wright-Patterson AFB OH, December 1988.
- [2] Johnston, Capt Dustin C. *A Dual-Port Digital Radio Frequency Memory*. MS thesis, AFIT/GE/ENG/89D-22. School of Engineering, Air Force Institute of Technology (AU), Wright-Patterson AFB OH, December 1989.
- [3] Kranz, Capt Gordon M. *Design of a 6-bit CMOS Digital Radio Frequency Memory Using Very Large Scale Integrated Circuit Technology*. MS thesis, AFIT/GE/ENG/90D-30. School of Engineering, Air Force Institute of Technology (AU), Wright-Patterson AFB OH, December 1990.
- [4] IEEE. *IEEE Standard VHDL Language Manual*. IEEE Std 1076-1987, The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, Inc., New York NY, 1988.
- [5] Gaughan, Daniel J. *Silicon Hybrid Wafer Scale Integration (WSI) Used to Fabricate a Hilbert Transform Integrated Circuit Module*. MS thesis, AFIT/GE/ENG/90D-22. School of Engineering, Air Force Institute of Technology (AU), Wright-Patterson AFB OH, December 1990.

Figure 1: Pipelined DRFM Architecture

Figure 2: Transfer Function of the VHDL Hilbert Transform Model

Figure 3: Frequency Plot of the VHDL DRFM Model

Figure 4: Time Domain Plot of the VHDL DRFM Model

Figure 5: Silicon Floor Plan of the DRFM Integrated Circuit